

Hydro-mechanical phase-field modeling of fluid-driven fracture in diamond-olivine systems: Reassessing the role of time-dependent inelastic deformation

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The entrapment pressure of mineral inclusions in diamonds is a key proxy for investigating Earth's interior conditions. Elastic geobarometry methods (Angel et al., 2022; Rustioni et al., 2015) assume that the diamond host behaves purely elastically during exhumation. However, observations from the Udachnaya kimberlite challenge this assumption, as olivine inclusions exhibit anomalously low residual pressures. Reconciling these observations with entrapment conditions requires a non-elastic pressure relaxation of approximately 30%, which cannot be explained by purely elastic models.

In previous work (Puhan, Alvaro, et al., 2024; Puhan et al., 2025; Puhan, Patton, et al., 2024), we investigated whether brittle fracture alone could account for this relaxation. Using extended finite element methods and dry phase-field modeling, we showed that brittle fracture under dry conditions provides insufficient pressure relaxation, leaving a gap between numerical predictions and natural observations.

A promising candidate to explain this discrepancy is the presence of fluid rims at the inclusion–host interface (Nimis et al., 2016), which may promote fluid-driven (“hydraulic”) fracturing at reduced stress thresholds. To investigate this mechanism, we developed a coupled hydro-mechanical phase-field formulation implemented in Abaqus via a user-defined element, building on porous-media-based damage frameworks (Li et al., 2022; Navidtehrani et al., 2025). This framework enables coupled simulations of fluid pressure build-up and fracture propagation, allowing direct comparison between dry and fluid-assisted relaxation scenarios.

Preliminary results indicate that although fluid rims enhance fracture nucleation compared to the dry case, the resulting pressure relaxation remains insufficient to reach the ~30% threshold required for Udachnaya samples. These findings suggest that brittle mechanisms alone cannot fully account for the observed pressure deficits. While plastic deformation is typically associated with super-deep diamonds (Alvaro et al., 2022), our results suggest that time-dependent inelastic deformation, involving both plastic and viscous components, may also contribute to post-entrapment stress relaxation under lithospheric conditions (Zhong et al., 2020).

REFERENCES

1. Alvaro, M., Angel, R. J., & Nestola, F. (2022). Inclusions in diamonds probe Earth's chemistry through deep time. *Communications Chemistry*, 5(1), 10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42004-022-00627-1>
2. Angel, R. J., Alvaro, M., & Nestola, F. (2022). Crystallographic Methods for Non-destructive Characterization of Mineral Inclusions in Diamonds. *Reviews in Mineralogy and Geochemistry*, 88(1), 257–305. <https://doi.org/10.2138/rmg.2022.88.05>
3. Li, H., Lei, H., Yang, Z., Wu, J., Zhang, X., & Li, S. (2022). A hydro-mechanical-damage fully coupled cohesive phase field model for complicated fracking simulations in poroelastic media. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 399, 115451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2022.115451>
4. Navidtehrani, Y., Betegón, C., & Martínez-Pañeda, E. (2025). A generalised framework for phase field-based modelling of coupled problems: Application to thermo-mechanical fracture, hydraulic fracture, hydrogen embrittlement and corrosion. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 326, 111363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2025.111363>
5. Nimis, P., Alvaro, M., Nestola, F., Angel, R. J., Marquardt, K., Rustioni, G., Harris, J. W., & Marone, F. (2016). First evidence of hydrous silicic fluid films around solid inclusions in gem-quality diamonds. *Lithos*, 260, 384–389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2016.05.019>
6. Puhan, B., Alvaro, M., Patton, A., Mazzucchelli, M. L., Reali, A., & Morganti, S. (2024, June 3). Investigation of microscale fracture opening in host inclusion systems. *ECCOMAS Congress 2024*. ECCOMAS Congress 2024, Lisbon. https://congressarchive.cimne.com/eccomas_2024/abstracts/120c3cf196dd11ee8a2d000c29ddfc0c.pdf
7. Puhan, B., Alvaro, M., Patton, A., Reali, A., & Morganti, S. (2025, May 1). Investigation of microscale brittle fracture opening in diamond with olivine inclusion using advanced computational modelling. *EGU General Assembly 2025*. EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-12235>
8. Puhan, B., Patton, A., Morganti, S., Rustioni, G., Reali, A., & Alvaro, M. (2024). Investigation of microscale brittle fracture opening in diamond with olivine inclusion using XFEM and cohesive zone modeling. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 110713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2024.110713>
9. Rustioni, G., Angel, R., Milani, S., Mazzucchelli, M., Nimis, P., Domeneghetti, M., Marone, F., Alvaro, M., Harris, J., & Nestola, F. (2015). Elastic geobarometry for host-inclusion systems: Pressure release and the role of brittle failure. *Rendiconti Online Della Società Geologica Italiana*, 35, 137.
10. Zhong, X., Moulas, E., & Tajčmanová, L. (2020). Post-entrapment modification of residual inclusion pressure and its implications for Raman elastic thermobarometry. *Solid Earth*, 11(1), 223–240. <https://doi.org/10.5194/se-11-223-2020>